

HRPP staff interview schedule

- Demographics
 - Practice type (e.g., mixed urban/rural)
 - Job description (e.g., Practice Nurse, Health Promotion Coordinator, Practice Manager, years of experience in the role)
- **How was your experience of the program?**
 - What did you like about it? What did you dislike about it?
- **Have you / has your practice ever provided supports like those offered in the programme before?**
 - How did the programme compare to those experiences?
- **How was the program run in your practice?**
 - Did your practice offer the programme in-person and /or virtually?
 - What were the pros/cons of these approaches?
 - Did you like that it was run from the practice? If yes / no, why?
 - How did the practice team manage running the program?
 - Were there any logistical challenges? (e.g., Covid, resources, funding, time constraints, patient demand etc...)
- **How do you think patients engaged with the programme?**
 - What factors played a role in terms of making patients more / less engaged?
 - Can you think of any strategies that might help make patients engage more with the programme?
- **How accessible was the programme for patients?**
 - What barriers / facilitators influenced the programme's accessibility?
 - Can you think of any strategies / initiatives to enhance the programme's accessibility?
- **How do you think the programme and initiatives like this impact your community / all Irish communities?**
 - Is there a need for more initiatives like this?
- **What can we learn from the programme going forward?**
 - Where do we go from here?
 - The programme runs for 24 months, due to finish early 2023. Should the programme be continued? Modified? Expanded?
- **Have you any other feedback you would like to give or things to talk about that these questions didn't address?**